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A Study on Factors Facilitating Access to Mobile Phone Money in Uganda

By

**Orotin P.
Quisenbery W.
Ted Sun**

Research Article

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***Orotin P., Quisenbery W. and Ted Sun**

Swiss Management Centre University, Transknowlogy Campus, Baarerstrasse 112, 6302 Zug, Switzerland.

*Corresponding Author's Email: patrickorotin2006@yahoo.co.uk

ABSTRACT

The convergence of mobile telephony and financial services has the potential to significantly expand access to financial services to individuals at the base of the pyramid. In Uganda, roughly 80 percent of the population has no access to banking services and mobile phone money, a financial service and transaction made on a mobile phone could address this financial gap. The focus of this phenomenological study was to explore access to mobile phone money in Uganda, in particular, from the experiences of 4 mobile network operators, 8 network agents and 19 mobile phone money users in Kampala district. The question for this research was: What are the factors influencing access to mobile phone money in Uganda? The conceptual framework for this study was based on Kim and Mauborgue's concept of Blue Ocean Strategy (Kim & Mauborgue, 2005). Key findings revealed that a wide network of agents was the most important factor for access to mobile phone money services. The most used mobile phone money service was transfer of money to relatives and friends. The main conclusion from this study is that mobile phone money has improved financial inclusion in Uganda as over 2 million adults who were previously unbanked are accessing financial services using their mobile phones.

Keywords: Base of the pyramid, Blue Ocean Strategy, market development, mobile phone money transfer, mobile phone money, phenomenological study, Uganda.

INTRODUCTION

The convergence of mobile telephony and financial services has the potential to significantly expand access to financial services for individuals at the base of the pyramid. According to the World Bank, 75 percent of the 3 billion poor people in the world do not have a bank account. Roughly 67 percent of the poor who do not have a bank account cite poverty as the obstacle to financial access. While about 33 percent blame the cost of opening and maintaining an account or the banks being too far away (World Bank, 2012). Mobile Phone Money Transfer, a financial service and transaction made on a mobile phone, could significantly fill this financial gap among the unbanked, especially in Africa (Must and Ludewig, 2010, United Nations, 2012). In Africa where the largest population of the unbanked live, only 53 percent compared to 79 percent in the developed world has access to mobile phones (Global Mobile Statistics, 2012).

In Kenya, where Safaricom Mobile Phone Company is believed to have been one of the first to start Mobile Phone Money, popularly known as "M-PESA," the relatively more stable socio-economic environment as well as the positive regulatory stance of the Central Bank of Kenya (CBK) has been instrumental in fostering faster Mobile Phone Money market development (IFC, 2011). Since its launch in March 2007, Safaricom M-PESA is used by roughly 15million people, which is about 36 percent of total Kenyan population. Reports from recent studies indicated that 84 percent of Kenyans say they would be worse off if M-PESA did not exist (Suri and Jack, 2011).

According to studies on Mobile Phone Money, Mobile Network Operators (MNOs) tend to grow their agent network in tandem with new customers to avoid diminishing agent incentives and causing drop-outs. Building agent networks from existing airtime resellers is one of the most successful approaches to Mobile Phone Money market development (Mas and Ng'weno, 2010; Kasseeah and Tandrayen-Ragoobur, 2012). For example, the extensive agent's network that is visible at almost every street of Nairobi in Kenya is one of the many reasons behind the success of Safaricom's M-PESA (Suri and Jack, 2011). Thus, Mobile Phone Money business built on a viable agent network model produces and maintains profitable growth for Mobile Phone Money offering beyond the existing

demand. Similarly, small stores reselling airtime are ubiquitous in many developing countries. These are potentially strong channels, partly because they are already receptive to mobile technologies. According to Heyer and Mas

(2009), working with these retailers is better than partnering with post office branches, which may be corrupt or mismanaged, and larger retail franchises, which may provide a good platform, but generally lack outreach in poorer villages. In countries where retailer coverage is low, there is usually a slow down in mobile money transfer growth, especially to the low income rural population (Olga and Pickens, 2009).

According to recent studies on Mobile Phone Money service fees, it is important to price the products and services appropriately to encourage client uptake, particularly if they are being introduced in a country for the first time (Mas and Ng'weno, 2010). Safaricom's pricing for M-PESA was designed to encourage customers to experiment: free and quick registration, free deposits, and the ability to send money to any mobile phone subscriber. Safaricom's profit margin is loaded on person-to-person (P2P) and, increasingly, person-to-business (P2B) transfer fees, not cash-in/cash-out fee, reflecting that customer willingness to pay seem to be higher for remote payments where alternatives are weakest. For example, Safaricom's M-PESA is only available to Safaricom subscribers (Suri and Jack, 2011). Consequently, if there is no credit on the SIM card, M-PESA does not work.

In Uganda, Mobile Phone Money transfer is a new phenomenon brought about by advancements in computer and telecommunication technologies. This has resulted in marked expansion in Mobile Phone Money over the last four years in a country where about 80 percent of the population lacks access to financial services (Ndiwalana, Olga, and Popv, 2010). Recent data show there are 30 banks in Uganda with a penetration of only 10 percent of the population (Bank of Uganda Annual Report, 2010/2011). Further, the communications infrastructure in Uganda in regards to Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) is unreliable. Many clients using ATMs have often been robbed of their funds through stealing of ATM Personal Identification Number (Bank of Uganda Annual Report, 2010/2011). Thus, ATMs are being perceived to be unreliable.

Currently, there are four Mobile Phone Money operators in Uganda, with MTN being the largest. Of the over 6 million Mobile Phone Money users, MTN has a market share of about 4 million with 7,336 MTN mobile money agents, Uganda Telecom (UTL) has 520,000 users with 3,500 M-Sente mobile money agents, Airtel has 120,000 users with 120 Zap mobile money agents, and Warid Telecom has 2 million users with 44 Pesa mobile money agents (Ministry of ICT status reports, 2012).. According to Ministry of ICT status reports 2012, overall daily Mobile Phone Money transfer in Uganda hit Ushs50billion (or US\$20million) by June 2012 up from Ushs30billion (US\$12million) in early 2011, signifying the important place Mobile Phone Money has in the financial market deepening in Uganda.

This research will attempt to provide evidence in support of the factors facilitating access to Mobile Phone Money in Uganda. In Uganda, there is no study that investigated factors facilitating access to Mobile Phone Money. Studies that have been conducted tended to concentrate on actual usage of Mobile Phone Money rather than on factors influencing access to Mobile Phone Money (Ndiwalana et al., 2010; Kyeyune, Kituyi and Miuro, 2012). So far such studies in the developing world have been done in Sri Lanka, Brazil, Thailand, Nigeria and Kenya (IFC, 2011).

This research is a strategic move to make Mobile Phone Money more compelling to policy makers as mobile phone services including Mobile Phone Money transfer accounted for 63 percent of the telecommunications revenue, contributed Ushs215 billion (US\$ 120 million) in tax revenue, making it the number one source of revenue for Uganda in 2011 (Uganda Communications Commission Market Review Report, 2012). Because Value Added Tax (VAT) is embedded in the cost of sending Mobile Phone Money, roughly 80 percent of the Uganda's unbanked population will be contributing to revenue generation and financial market development through access to Mobile Phone Money services. It will also shape the policy environment that has propelled rapid growth in the Mobile Phone Money sector elsewhere in the world (Yabs, 2010; IFC, 2011), and help Uganda's leaders to move from strategy to effective implementation of Mobile Phone Money. Thus, a qualitative phenomenological research study that explores factors influencing access to Mobile Phone money could address the problem. The general purpose of this research is to generate a phenomenological study. Specifically, the purpose isto bring into light factors influencing access to Mobile Phone moneyin Uganda, and to contribute to a body of knowledge of mobile commerce that serves as a basis for reference by researchers and policy makers. The main question this research intends to answer is: What are the factors influencing access to mobile phone money in Uganda?

This study is guided by Kim and Mauborgne's concept of Blue Ocean Strategy (Kim and Mauborgne, 2005) with focus on untapped market space, demand creation, and opportunity for highly profitable growth. Guided by this concept, this study will provide only practical analytics for the factors influencing access to the Mobile Phone money in Uganda. This research does not provide a historical account of Mobile Phone Money development, nor does it provide a detailed account of Mobile Phone Money transfer services. Instead it focuses more narrowly on the factors influencing access to the Mobile Phone money in Uganda, and particularly on the lived experiences of users with Mobile Phone Money.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research design

A qualitative phenomenological research design was adopted for this study. A research applying phenomenology is concerned with the lived experiences of the people involved with the issue that is being researched (Caelli, 2001; Casey, 2000; Ehrich, 2005; Groenewald, 2004; Heath, 2000; Mason, 2010; Nitta, Holley, and Wrobel, 2010; Rinyka, 2012; Robson, 2002). The purpose of a phenomenological approach is to illuminate the specific, to identify phenomena through how they are perceived by the actors. Using this research design, multiple data collection techniques can be used, including; interviews, conversations, participant observation, document research, analysis of text (Groenewald, 2004) and presentation of multiple realities with the researcher as the instrument of data collection, with a focus on participants' views. Adding an interpretive dimension to this research through the phenomenological approach enabled results to be used as a basis for practical theory, allowing it to inform, support or challenge policy and action.

Study location

The study was conducted in Kampala district in central Uganda. Kampala district was chosen as the study location not only because it has the largest number of Mobile Phone Money agents and users, but also diverse socio-economic characteristics and distributions of Mobile Phone Money operators, agents and users in the country, making it a best choice for this study. All the four Mobile Phone Money operators have their head offices in Kampala. Micro enterprises make up the largest share (92.4%) of the total number of businesses in Kampala, followed by small enterprises at 5.3 percent, and least being large enterprises at 0.2 percent (UBOS, 2009). This indicates that a greater population of Kampala district is largely of low income earners. The large proportion of low income earners presents a huge opportunity for Mobile Phone Money operators to extend this relatively cheap financial service to this group through Mobile Phone Money.

Research question

The research question this study intends to answer is: What are the factors influencing access to Mobile Phone Money in Uganda?

Selection of participants

The participants for this phenomenological study consisted of Mobile Phone Money operators, Mobile Phone Money agents and Mobile Phone Money users, selected using criterion sampling (Creswell, 2007). According to Creswell, criterion sampling works well for phenomenological studies because it is essential for all participants selected to have experienced the phenomenon that is under investigation. In this study, experiences with Mobile Phone Money dictated the method, including even the type of participants.

Sample size

A purposive sampling was chosen, described by Groenewald (2004) as the most important kind of non-probability sampling to identify the primary participants for a phenomenological study. The study sample for this study was selected based on the researcher's judgment and the purpose of the research, looking for those who have experiences with Mobile Phone Money phenomenon to be researched. Use was made of Internet searches and physical inquiry to the MNOs' offices to identify Mobile Phone Money shop locations and the right people to interview about Mobile Phone Money. The criterion used for selecting participants for this study were as follows: (a) Mobile Network Operators (MNO) which were currently offering platforms for Mobile Phone Money transfer in Uganda, (b) Mobile Phone Money agents who were currently offering Mobile Phone Money services, and (c) Users who were currently using Mobile Phone Money services. To meet this criterion, the MNO must be licensed to provide Mobile Phone Money services; the Mobile Phone Money agents must have an agreement with MNO (i.e. registered, has a premise, and trained in Mobile Phone Money offerings and procedures). MNOs, Mobile Phone Money agents and Mobile Phone Money users who met this criterion were selected to participate in this study. Based on the above arguments, Mertens and McLaughlin (2004) suggested that the appropriate number of participants for a

phenomenological research is six. Creswell (2007) suggested 10 participants as adequate for a phenomenological research; while Morse (2000) and Salkind (2005) on the other hand suggested 30 participants. In this study, the

sample size went up to 31 participants because the researcher wanted to capture the significant experiences of the participants with the four Mobile Phone Money platforms. Thus, it was important to draw experiences in involvement of participants with all the four Mobile Phone Money platforms, viz; Mobile Telephone Network (MTN) Uganda, Airtel, Uganda Telecom (UTL) and Warid Telecom. Four MNOs, 8 Mobile Phone Money agents and 19 Mobile Phone Money users were therefore selected to participate in this study.

Research Instruments

For phenomenological studies, the researcher is often the sole person responsible for data collection and for the design of the instruments that will be used to collect data. In this study, the researcher was also the research instrument, especially where he played the role of a data collection instrument during research participants' observation. In this study, data were collected from individuals. According to Colin Robson (2002), individual interviews are generally the principal source of data collection for phenomenological studies. By using interviews, a deeper understanding of the lived experiences of the participants with Mobile Phone Money emerged.

Data Collection Procedures

The interview questions were directed to the participants' experiences, feelings, beliefs and convictions about access to Mobile Phone Money. According to Caelli (2001), Davidson (2000) and Groenewald (2004), this technique is called bracketing when the research is performed from the perspective of the research participant. Bracketing in this study entailed asking MNOs, Mobile Phone Money agents and users to share their lived experiences with access to Mobile Phone Money based on the open-ended interview guides. In addition, 'memoing' was used in data gathering in this study. Using this technique, field notes recording were taken of what the researcher heard, observed, experienced and thought in the course of collecting data and reflecting in the process. And because there were multiple realities, the research questions kept on being modified in the process (Robson, 2002, p.27). Data collection interviews continued until the topic was exhausted or saturated; that is when interviewees introduced no new perspectives on access to Mobile Phone Money. This was also a form of data validation.

Data Storage

Field notes are a secondary data storage method and crucial in qualitative research to retain data gathered. Field notes were written in the evening of the same day that field interviews were conducted to avoid memory loss. The method of field note taking followed the model described by Groenewald (2004), which included: Observation notes (ON) – 'what happened notes' deemed important enough to the researcher to make, Theoretical notes (TN) - 'attempts to derive meaning' as the researcher thinks or reflects on experiences of the research participants, Methodological notes (MN) – 'reminds, instructions or critique' to oneself on the process of data gathering, analytical memos (AM) – end of a field day summary or progress reviews. In cases where secondary data have been used, all sources have been properly acknowledged and, where specific authorization was required to access such information, such authorization was sought from the responsible authority.

Data Analysis

From a phenomenological research perspective, it is important to recognize that field notes written during field interviews and observations are already a step toward data analysis. Groenewald (2004, p. 16) comments that since field notes involve interpretation, they are properly speaking, "part of the analysis rather than data collection." There is usually no need to analyse them further. According to Groenewald (2004), the term 'analysis' usually means breaking into parts, and therefore often means a loss of the whole phenomenon, and should be used carefully in phenomenological studies. Accordingly, the data analysis method used in this phenomenological research followed that described by Groenewald (2004, p. 17), which included; bracketing and phenomenological reduction, not allowing the researcher's meanings and interpretations or theoretical concepts to enter the unique views of the research participants, delineating units of meaning from those statements from the research participants or documents that were seen to illuminate the researched phenomena were extracted or isolated, clustering of units of meaning to form themes; summarizing each interview, validating it and where necessary modifying it; extracting general and unique themes from all the interviews and making a composite summary.

When all the above processes had been done for all the individual interviews, the researcher looked for the themes common to most or all of the interviews as well as the individual variations. The themes were the basis for data description, analysis and interpretation based on the research question posed for this phenomenological study.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Although access to financial services through Mobile Phone Money payments has expanded, this has not yet reached a significant scale. Overall, Mobile Phone Money access is still limited when contrasted with its apparent promises of reaching the unbanked and underserved, of servicing existing banking clients, and of being a means for redeeming a cashless society. The study examined the following in more detail: Factors influencing access to Mobile Phone Money in Uganda, with reference to: country regulations, existing access to financial market services and access to mobile phone market. The research question guiding this paper is: What are the factors influencing access to Mobile Phone Money in Uganda? This paper provides detailed information regarding three main topics as they relate to access to Mobile Phone Money in Uganda, namely; Regulations, Access to Mobile Phone Market and Potential demand for Mobile Phone Money in Uganda.

Demographic Statistics

The profile of the Mobile Phone Money respondents is shown in Figure 1. The Mobile Phone Money user respondents can be summarized as follows: slightly more than 50 percent are females; 96 percent are between 18-30 years of age. This is the age range for people regarded as youth in Uganda. None of the respondents was younger than 18 years. In Uganda, a person below 18 years is regarded as a child, and employing such a person amounts to child labour (UBOS, 2009). About 44 percent have a university degree, and slightly more than 40 percent are still students. More than 30 percent are employees of private businesses; and family business make up slightly more than 40 percent of the occupation of Mobile Phone Money users. This is not surprising as research indicates that family businesses have been some of the drivers of the world’s most developed economies, such as the USA, India and China (Awis and Zongjun, 2010).

Figure 1: Demographic Characteristics of Mobile Phone Money Users
Source: Mobile Phone Money Transfer Study 2012

This study was not intended to be a statistically significant sample of Mobile Phone Money users in Uganda. Its purpose was to provide an in-depth qualitative analysis of the access of users to Mobile Phone Money, and the potential for expanded access to Mobile Phone Money in Uganda. The study involved face-to-face interviews with 27 Mobile Phone Money agents and users in Kampala City and its suburbs, and the 4 major Mobile Phone Money Operators (MMOs) in Kampala (i.e. MTN Uganda, Airtel, Warid Telecom and UTL). Respondents were interviewed in 6 locations in and around Kampala City, 3 of which represented the urban setting, while the other 3 represented the semi-urban setting. This ensured a good representation of the socio-economic background of the respondents. Areas where interviews were conducted included; market areas, business areas, trading centres, petrol stations, as well as those areas close to supermarkets and banks. In Uganda, the main use of Mobile Phone Money is for remittances to relatives or families, provided by Mobile Phone Money and additional access channel for people with existing bank accounts. Non-bank account holders use Mobile Phone Money mainly for Person-to-Person (P2P) transfer. The proportion of the unbanked (28 percent) is slightly smaller (see Figure 2) given that the semi-urban centres where this study was conducted have been influenced into use of banking by being near Kampala City.

Figure 2: Ownership of Bank Accounts among users of Mobile Phone Money
Source: Mobile Phone Money Study 2012

Regulations

Bank of Uganda has less regulatory control over MNOs other than MNOs using the banking system for liquidity management. This is similar to what the Central Bank of Kenya did to Safaricom's M-PESA (Mas & Ng'weno, 2010). Like the Central Bank of Kenya, the Central Bank of Uganda allowed Mobile Phone Money to start and operate outside the provisions of the existing banking laws, as it continued to work out laws and rules to control this branchless banking. This allowed free competition with commercial banks and thus facilitated Mobile Phone Money to spread rapidly in Uganda, with 552,047 people accessing the service in 2009 to about 6,000,000 people by August 2012, a ten-fold increase over a period of 4 years.

Uganda was the first developing country to liberalise the communications sector. In 1996, the government established a telecommunications policy to guide the liberalized sector. Known as the Exclusivity/Duopoly Policy, the framework focused on the provision of infrastructure under minimum competition. Limited competition was a key strategy pillar in attracting private sector investment at a time when the market size was assumed to be small. In 2006, Uganda opened up the sector fully to competition, thus making an end to the five-year duopoly policy. This was capped by the creation of the Ministry of ICT in June 2006. Uganda now has technology-neutral licensing regime characterized by two main categories of licenses: Public Service Provider (PSP) and Public Infrastructure Provider (PIP). Accordingly, Uganda's communications sector is one of the fastest growing in Africa. To-date, the number of mobile phone subscribers stands at about 17 million; almost half of Uganda's 33 million people have a phone, compared to the fixed line market with slightly over 400,000 customers (see Table 1).

Table 1: Uganda Telecommunications Sector Key Statistics, 2009-2011

Description	Period		
	2009	2010	2011
Total population	31,000,000	31,783,953	32,940,194
Fixed Phones Subscriptions	263,370	327,114	464,849
Mobile Phone Subscriptions	9,336,630	12,828,264	16,696,992
Teledensity/Fixed & Mobile Phone Penetration (%)*	31%	41.4 %	52.1%

Teledensity/Mobile Phone Penetration (%)*	30%	40%	50%
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Source: UCC Annual Review Report 2012. *Derived as total number of phone subscriptions divided by total population x 100%.

This is a significant growth compared to the 12 million fixed and mobile voice telephony customers in 2010, and to 9.6 million in 2009. By December 2011, the teledensity, a composite of mobile and fixed lines stood at 52.1 percent compared to 41.4 percent in 2010 and 31 percent in 2009 (see Table 1). The mobile phone is a conduit for mobile phone money transfer. Thus the 17 million people owning the phone handset means more people can now access financial service through their mobile phones should they all be registered.

Mobile Phone Money Deployments

The first Mobile Money operation in Uganda was launched in March 2009 and has become the most famous and probably the most successful implementation of Mobile Phone Money service to date. By December 2011, thirty-six months after the launch, Mobile Phone Money transfer in Uganda had reached 2,879,968 registered customers and almost 6,000 agents. By August 2012, forty-one months after the launch, Mobile Phone Money had gained over 6 million registered customers and had over 11,000 agents (an average of 109 Mobile Phone Money agents per district) spread across Uganda compared to the banks' 455 branches (or average of 5 bank branches per district). Almost all MNOs in Uganda are investing in Mobile Phone Money. It brings in extra revenue and just as importantly, breeds stickier relationships in a fickle market where 'pay-as-you-go' customers often hold SIM cards from several different MNOs at once. Banks traditionally have to set up a branch. All MNOs have to do is to set up a Tower; the relationship with the customer is already in place. Since 2009, there has been successive deployment of Mobile Phone Money, with MTN being the first to add Mobile Phone Money to its phone services, followed by Uganda Telecom, Airtel and Warid Telecom (see Table 2). MTN Mobile money is by far the most successful mobile money deployment in Uganda. Since its commercial launch in March 2009, it has been adopted by over 4 million customers, corresponding to 51 percent of the 7.7 million MTN mobile phone subscriber base and 23 percent of the 17 million total mobile phone subscriptions in Uganda.

Table 2: *Mobile Phone Money Deployments in Uganda 2009-2011*

Launched in March 2009		Launched in March 2010		Launched in July 2011		Launched in Dec 2011	
Promotor	Brand Name	Promotor	Brand Name	Promotor	Brand Name	Promotor	Brand Name
MTN Uganda	MTN Mobile Money	Uganda Telecom	M-Sente	Airtel Uganda	Zap	Warid Telecom	Warid Pesa

Source: MNO Websites

The MTN service is reaching 12 percent of Uganda's population and 15 percent of all unbanked persons. There are more than 75 times the number of MTN Mobile Money outlets/agents (7, 336) than the number of Microfinance Depositing Institutions (98), 42 times the number of money remitters (173), 22 times the number of Postal Bank branches (334), 16 times the number of commercial bank branches (455) and 12 times the number of ATMs (637) in Uganda in 2012.

UTL M-Sente which was launched in March 2010 is the second most successful Mobile Phone Money deployment. Since its commercial launch, it has been adopted by over 520, 000 customers, corresponding to 30 percent of the 1.7 million UTL mobile phone subscriber base and 10 percent of the 17 million total mobile phone subscriptions in Uganda in 2011. M-Sente services now reach 1 percent of Uganda's population and 1 percent of all unbanked persons. There are more than 10 times the number of UTL M-Sente agents or outlets (3, 500) than the total number of Postal Bank branches (334), 8 times the number of commercial bank branches (455) and 5 times the number of ATMs (637) in 2012.

Airtel Zap is another upcoming Mobile Phone Money deployment. Since its commercial launch in July 2011, it has been adopted by over 120, 000 customers, corresponding to 3 percent of the 4 million mobile phone subscriber base. Its reach to the Uganda's unbanked persons is yet insignificant.

Agent Networks

On the streets of Kampala City in Uganda, one would not walk past 2 or 3 shops without seeing a sign post reading, "Mobile Money services available here." This may be in a shop, a store, or in supermarkets. Mobile Phone Money agents are widely distributed, visible and well supported by their supervisors. One of the supervisors or super agent is Go Phone, which has a network of sub-agents around Kampala City. On the ground, the agents or sub-agents

represent the presence and scale of operation of the Mobile Phone Money brand. For example, observations across different institutions in Kampala City and the suburbs indicate the presence of Mobile Phone Money in banks, microcredit institutions, Telco service centres, to specialized agents and individuals. Because of the wide spread network of agents, one does not need to go far to use the services of a Mobile Phone Money. This makes life so easy for users.

There are 'Authorized Dealers' for a particular MNO. These are strictly for the MNO that it has signed an agreement with to buy and sell its products only, including transacting in the MNO's Mobile Phone Money. They usually deal in large amounts of Mobile Money transfers, and well guarded by security personnel. The other category is 'retailer shops' that are registered by existing MNO's agents. It was surprising to observe that these retailer shops did not engage any guard or security personnel to protect them from any eventual theft of money. Asked whether that was not risky, agents that were involved in the interview had this to say: *Theft has not yet occurred. We do not expect that it will happen because most Mobile Phone Money transactions are usually small and within average of Ushs 50,000 (US\$20) per transaction. Moreover, we keep on banking the money as the transactions proceed during the course of the day.*" It was not surprising to see most retailer shops located near petrol stations, banks, supermarkets, or some busy centre. These businesses usually employ security personnel which retailer shops take advantage of.

Retailer shops are not under any obligation to sell only one MNO products. They are free to transact with any MNO, be it MTN, Airtel, Warid or UTL. Consequently, there is no exclusive relationship between airtime agents and MNO, which distorts some of the control that MNOs might have over their agents. With the fast adoption of Mobile Phone Money in Uganda, MNOs began reducing commission for their airtime agents network and allowing subscribers to top up their accounts using their mobile phones. This arrangement would reduce the incentive for airtime agents to promote Mobile Phone Money. MNOs are now selling fewer scratch cards as Mobile Phone Money takes off. MTN in particular, does not see any competitive advantage in promoting airtime agents network. The Mobile Phone Money agent networks that other MNOs are developing that sidestep their current airtime networks add emphasis to the MTN argument.

Retailer Sector

Every retail shop in Uganda almost sells airtime. The retail shops that exist in every trading centre and, mobile phone networks that are widely distributed across the country provide the necessary infrastructure that facilitates access to mobile financial services by a larger segments of the unbanked poor people. This branchless banking model is taking small-value transactions out of the banking halls into retail shops, where cash-in/cash-out merchants, such as airtime vendors, petrol station attendants and shopkeepers register new accounts and covert customers' cash into electronic value and vice versa.

Clients can covert cash into electronic money and vice versa through these retail shops and outlets. They can then use their mobile phones to instantaneously send and receive money wherever they have mobile network coverage. The transaction information is then communicated back to the Mobile Network Operator or bank. The customer needs to visit a retail outlet or shop only for transactions that involve depositing or withdrawing cash. This was evident in all the Mobile Phone Money shops visited for interviews; all the transactions observed were those of depositing or withdrawing cash. In formal banking, these activities are all carried out in a bank. By taking small-value transactions out of the banking halls into retail shops, MNOs have chosen a strategy that will take banks creativity and innovation to copy and be able to perform it effectively. Consequently, use of retailer sector which is closer to the poorer community has enabled access to mobile phone money services by this largely poor segments of the population.

Pricing

Because of the short transaction process involved in Mobile Phone Money transfer, the platform has become a very attractive investment for retailer shops and users. As there are no entry and re-entry barriers to establish a retail outlet, stiff competition amongst the MNOs has led to price differentiation. Some MNOs have lowered the price of sending and withdrawing money to attract and retain customers to the network by applying costs reduction in the value chain system (Kim and Mauborgue, 2005).

Desk research, brochures obtained from MNOs and observations of the price lists posted on the wall of the agents shops showed there were different tariffs for sending (cash-in) and withdrawing (cash-out) money. This was seen with MTN Mobile Money, UTL M-Sente and Airtel Zap non-registered users not being charged any fee for withdrawing money from any of their network of agents (see Table 3).

This exemption was posted on all the walls of the stores operated by the three Mobile Phone Money operators. The plot here was to be registered so that you pay a lesser charge for transferring money. In other words, it was a strategy for attracting more customers and retaining existing ones.

According to Michael E. Porter, pricing form one part of an industry's value chain system. By modeling the value system for the entire Telco industry, MNOs were able to assess how significant pricing was to their Mobile Phone Money industry's impact and could link it to the entire value chain (Porter, 1985). In applying Porter's value chain model, MTN Uganda sold off 1, 000 of its Tower sites to be managed by American Tower Corporation (ATC). This reduced costs in the whole value chain system, including Mobile Phone Money business, although the figures of what this could be were not available. What was certain is that additional margins have been freed up from which MTN has taken a greater share of the Mobile Phone Money market in Uganda. This was seen in the rise in MTN's customer base.

Table 3: Consumer Tariffs of the four Mobile Phone Money providers in Uganda

1. MTN Mobile Money	Sending (cash-in) to:		Withdrawal (cash-out) by:	
Transaction tiers	Registered Subscriber	Non-Registered Subscriber	Registered Subscriber	Non-Registered Subscriber
Ushs	Ushs	Ushs	Ushs	0
500-5,000	400	800	300	0
5,001-30,000	800	1,600	700	0
30,001-60,000	800	2,000	1,000	0
60,001-125,000	800	3,700	1,600	0
125,001-250,000	800	7,200	3,000	0
250,001-500,000	800	10,000	5,000	0
500,001-1,000,000	800	19,000	9,000	0
1,000,001-2,000,000	800	36,000	17,200	0
2,000,001-3,000,000	800	64,000	31,200	0
3,000,001-4,000,000	800	64,000	31,000	0
2. UTL M-Sente	Sending (cash-in) to:		Withdrawal (cash-out) by:	
Transaction tiers	Registered Subscriber	Non-Registered Subscriber	Registered Subscriber	Non-Registered Subscriber
Ushs	Ushs	Ushs	Ushs	0
5,000-30,000	700	1,500	700	0
30,001-60,000	700	1,900	900	0
60,000-125,000	700	3,500	1,500	0
125,000-250,000	700	6,800	2,900	0
250,001-500,000	700	9,000	4,900	0
500,000-1,000,000	700	18,000	8,900	0
1,000,001-2,000,000	700	35,000	17,000	0
2,000,001-4,000,000	700	0	0	0
4,000,001-10,000,000	700	0	0	0
3. Airtel Zap	Sending (cash-in) to:		Withdrawal (cash-out) by:	
Transaction tiers	Registered Subscriber	Non-Registered Subscriber	Registered Subscriber	Non-Registered Subscriber

		Subscriber		
Ushs	Ushs	Ushs	Ushs	0
500-5,000	300	300	250	0
5,001-30,000	800	1,600	700	0
30,001-60,000	800	2,000	1,000	0
60,001-125,000	800	3,700	1,600	0
125,001-250,000	800	7,200	3,000	0
250,001-500,000	800	10,000	5,000	0
500,001-1,000,000	800	19,000	9,000	0
4. Warid Pesa	Sending (cash-in) to:		Withdrawal (cash-out) by:	
Transaction tiers	Registered Subscriber	Non-Registered Subscriber	Registered Subscriber	Non-Registered Subscriber
Ushs	Ushs	Ushs	Ushs	
500-15,000	700	800	700	1,600
15,001-30,000	800	900	700	1,700
30,001-60,000	800	900	1,000	2,100
60,001-125,000	800	900	1,600	3,800
125,001-250,000	800	900	3,000	7,500
250,001-500,000	800	900	5,000	10,000
500,001-1,000,000	800	900	9,000	19,000
1,000,001-2,000,000	1,200	1,300	14,000	30,000
2,000,000-3,000,000	2,000	2,100	22,000	38,000

Source: MNO Websites

Estimates put MTN Mobile Money customer base at over 4 million by August 2012 up from 2 million in 2011. Through the cost reduction strategy, MTN has been able to lower prices for Mobile Phone Money transactions for registered users who send money (cash-in) – the most used transaction; and non-registered subscribers who withdraw money in any MTN agent's shop (see Table 2). Most of MTN's registered users are urban-based and, some non-registered subscribers who use Mobile Phone Money services are rural-based. Thus, MTN is combining the strategy of pricing and target group to retain existing customers and reach more unbanked customers with Mobile Phone Money services at a target cost (Kim and Mauborgue, 2005).

Mobile Phone Money Services Used

From interviews with agents and observations of research participants at the Mobile Phone Money shops, the top four Mobile Phone Money services used by research participants are; fund transfer to friends and relatives, cash withdrawal and payment of water and electricity bills (see Figure 3). The results from these findings are consistent with those from studies on Mobile Phone Money use in other African countries. Fund transfer was also the most used service with M-PESA in Kenya (Mas and Ng'weno, 2010), MTN in Nigeria and True Money Express (TMX) in Thailand (IFC, 2011). This confirms the important role Mobile Phone Money can play in facilitating access to financial services for the unbanked in developing countries (Ndiwalana, Olga, and Popv, 2010; Kasseeah and Tandrayen-Ragoobur, 2012). Recent results from studies of most used Mobile Phone Money service in other developed countries like Brazil present the opposite of the scenario of the Mobile Phone Money transfer findings in Uganda.

Figure 3: Profile of Mobile Phone Money Use in Uganda

Source: Mobile Phone Money Study 2012

In Brazil where bank penetration is about 43 percent of the population, almost 33 percent more than that in Uganda, payment for public transport was the most used Mobile Phone Money service (IFC, 2011). This is not surprising. In Brazil, the several entities such as supermarkets, pharmacies, car dealers and lottery houses act as corresponding bank branches. These points provide convenient places where ATMs can be used to withdraw money easily. These reduce the need for cash transfer using Mobile Phone Money. Transporters can easily access their payments from the nearest retail point using their ATM cards (IFC, 2011).

From the interviews, payment of salaries/wages, taxes and loans using Mobile Phone Money in Uganda was still at the development stage (see Figures 4 & 5), although several informal businesses are using Mobile Phone Money for paying wages to their workers (see Figure 5). The perception of Government of Uganda in the use of Mobile Phone Money to channel payments to civil servants is still low. The appearance of reports of fraud by internal MNO staff on official media could delay any attempt by government to try this mechanism for channeling salaries to workers.

Figure 4: Kinds of Bills currently paid using Mobile Phone Money in Uganda

Source: Mobile Phone Money Study 2012

Figure 5: Kinds of Mobile Phone Money transfers in Uganda

Source: Mobile Phone Money Study 2012

CONCLUSIONS

As outlined previously, mobile phone money is advancing access to financial services, and is enabling access to financial services outside the existing traditional banking demands. It has provided a more efficient channel for financial transaction and inclusion in Uganda. As this study reveals, Mobile Phone Money also reaches the poor, as over 2 million Ugandans who are not banked are accessing informal financial service using their mobile phones. Even those who live on less than US\$2 a day are using Mobile Phone Money services to transfer money to their relatives or friends, but banks are commonly used by those who earn more than US\$2 a day. Currently, there is no specific financial regulation for Mobile Phone Money in Uganda, leaving most users at the mercy of MNOs. This is a gap that needs to be addressed directly.

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